

#2: Climate tipping points and their driving processes

Thanks to recent developments in Earth System Models (ESMs), the scientific knowledge on climate tipping points has been gradually expanding. Each new generation of ESMs provides a more nuanced picture, attempting to address different model biases and deficiencies. However, much is still unknown and the robustness and realism of the models' findings remain a key challenge. The processes and interactions that may trigger climate tipping points are not yet fully understood, and existing models' findings are not fully aligned on the tipping thresholds.

Action

TipESM will capitalise on the recent ESMs improvements. The most recent ESM archives, including archives of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6), will be scanned using novel algorithms in order to examine, isolate, and catalogue the chains of interactions leading to tipping events. The simulated changes and tipping signals will be further evaluated against observations and data on ancient climate (paleo-data).

By comparing when tipping points occur in various simulations, TipESM will extend the understanding of relevant thresholds, including the impacts of different model biases and noise on estimating these thresholds. This will result in a better understanding of the risks of tipping in specific Earth system phenomena.

Studying driving processes of tipping points

There are several steps that TipESM will take to research the driving processes of climate tipping points using ESMs. First, we will use a set of scripts, statistical tests and a machine learning algorithm to identify tipping points in the catalogued simulations. Once identified, the tipping points will be analysed to pinpoint the causal chains in which feedbacks quickly amplify, inducing tipping in specific domains, e.g. ice sheets melting, Amazon dieback, or permafrost thawing. The tipping points models will be benchmarked against observations to identify possible model biases that may increase, decrease or even prevent the occurrence of tipping points in current Earth System Models. Furthermore, lagged regressions will be used to find drivers for threshold crossing in mean climate and weather extremes associated with tipping.

By focusing on the driving processes of climate tipping points, TipESM will:

- Update previous and ongoing efforts to document tipping points and abrupt changes in Earth System Models
- Isolate the feedbacks and chains of processes leading to tipping events
- Investigate climate thresholds that lead to tipping in ecosystems and society
- Develop a new risk-landscape for tipping events, including guidance for pathways to minimize those risks

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TipESM - Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

Project partners and associated partners

- Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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